

STUDIES ON PHOSPHATE FERTILIZERS. PART I. REACTIONS OF TRICALCIUM PHOSPHATE WITH ALKALI BISULPHATES

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The reactions of tricalcium phosphate with alkali bisulphates in aqueous medium are described. The reaction takes place with the initial formation of citrate-soluble calcium hydrogen phosphate which further reacts with the acid sulphate forming primary alkali phosphate. The secondary phosphate is formed in the presence of insufficient quantity of acid sulphate. The mechanism of the reactions is discussed.

A simple method based upon these reactions is suggested for the preparation of mixed fertilizers from phosphate rock and acid sulphates with some saving of sulphuric acid.

The phosphate fertilizers are made by treating rock phosphate with sulphuric acid; concentrated phosphate fertilizers are prepared by reacting rock phosphate with phosphoric acid. Considerable work¹⁻⁵ has been done on the systems: calcium oxide-phosphorus pentoxide and water and calcium oxide-phosphorus pentoxide-sulphur trioxide and water in order to understand the nature of the products formed under different conditions in the above two processes.

The present paper deals with the reaction of tricalcium phosphate with alkali bisulphates in aqueous medium, which provides preliminary data on the system: Na_2O (or K_2O) + CaO + P_2O_5 + SO_3 + H_2O .

EXPERIMENTAL

Tricalcium phosphate (pure), sodium bisulphate (81.2% NaHSO_4) and potassium bisulphate (pure) were used. Sodium bisulphate was supplied by the Hyderabad Chemicals and Fertilizers Ltd. The phosphate was determined by the ammonium phosphomolybdate method. Calcium was observed to interfere in the precipitation of ammonium phosphomolybdate with high results. However, if this precipitate is dissolved in ammonium citrate solution and reprecipitated, the precipitate of ammonium phosphomolybdate obtained becomes free of calcium and the results of estimation agree with those obtained by the pyrophosphate method. In view of the fact that the precipitation of ammonium phosphomolybdate is very slow, and usually never complete, the precipitate should be kept overnight to ensure its completion. The other conditions of precipitation are as prescribed in the

standard books of analysis⁶, viz. (i) temperature for precipitation, 60°-65° (ii) addition of nitric acid to acidify not in excess and (iii) washing the precipitate with ammonium nitrate solution.

Procedure.—Mixtures of pure tricalcium phosphate (about 1 g.) and sodium bisulphate in different proportions were accurately weighed and placed in a conical flask. Nearly 100 ml. of water was added; it was well shaken with a mechanical shaker for an hour at room temperature (25°-28°). The soluble portion was separated by filtration and the insoluble portion was subsequently washed several times with water. The water-insoluble portion was treated with ammonium citrate solution. The solutions together with washings were made up to a known volume. An aliquot of each solution was used for phosphate analysis. The results are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Reaction of tricalcium phosphate and alkali bisulphates in aqueous medium.

Proportion of the reactants		% Water-soluble phosphate.	% Citrate-soluble phosphate.	Proportion of the reactants		% Water-soluble phosphate.	% Citrate-soluble phosphate.
by wt.	by mols.			by wt.	by mols.		
$\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 + \text{NaHSO}_4$				$\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 + \text{KHSO}_4$			
1 : 1.57	1 : 3.3	100	Nil	1 : 0.5	1 : 1.14	27.05	9.99
1 : 1.5	1 : 3.15	70	6	1 : 1	1 : 2.28	52.79	15.15
1 : 1	1 : 2.1	49.5	20	1 : 1.5	1 : 3.42	82.60	5.66
				1 : 2	1 : 4.56	90.48	...

DISCUSSION

Table I indicates that with increasing proportion of the bisulphate the citrate-soluble phosphate content decreases and water-soluble phosphate increases, *i.e.*, the reaction between tricalcium phosphate and alkali bisulphate takes place with initial formation of the citrate-soluble calcium hydrogen phosphate, which further reacts with acid sulphate to produce water-soluble alkali phosphate. These reactions probably take place in aqueous medium as shown below :

When tricalcium phosphate and alkali bisulphate are allowed to react in dilute aqueous medium, the system will ordinarily consist of the following ions: R^+ , Ca^{2+} , HPO_4^{2-} , $H_2PO_4^-$ and SO_4^{2-} ; Ca^{2+} will react with the acidic ions to form more insoluble products, e.g. $CaHPO_4$ and $CaSO_4$ in preference to $CaH_2(PO_4)_2$. In presence of excess of acid sulphate, further reaction between $CaHPO_4$ and $NaHSO_4$ will take place. The overall process may be represented by the equations:

It will be seen that according to these equations, for obtaining cent per cent water-soluble phosphate, 3 moles of acid sulphate are required per mole of tricalcium phosphate. Against this theoretical requirement of acid sulphate, the actual quantity of acid sulphate needed is slightly greater than 3 moles of acid sulphate, i.e. between 3 and 4 moles of acid sulphate per mole of calcium phosphate. This presumably indicates that a side reaction in which 4 moles of the acid sulphate react with one mole of tricalcium phosphate is also taking place to a certain extent (equation 5).

The three equations representing three possible ways in which tricalcium phosphate and alkali bisulphate could react are set out below for comparison. It is presumed that all the three reactions are taking place to some extent and the phosphate is decomposed to primary and secondary phosphate in presence of excess of acidity and to dicalcium phosphate when insufficient acid sulphate is added.

The following experiment was carried out to confirm the formation of $CaHPO_4$. The reaction was allowed to take place between tricalcium phosphate and sodium bisulphate in 1 : 1 proportion by weight in aqueous medium, and Na_2HPO_4 that was formed was separated by filtration. The residue consisted of calcium sulphate and calcium hydrogen phosphate. The former being soluble in excess of water, it could be washed away with water till the residue gave no test for sulphate and consisted of only calcium hydrogen phosphate. The residue was dried and the amount of calcium was found out in it by the standard method¹. Total calcium found in the residue was 35.5% which was higher than the theoretical amount of calcium (29.4%) in dicalcium hydrogen phosphate. This may be due to the unchanged tricalcium phosphate in the residue.

This process provides a method⁸ for the production of primary, secondary and tertiary orthophosphates of the general formulae RH_2PO_4 , R_2HPO_4 and R_3PO_4 and mixed phosphates. Mixed phosphates are produced if hydroxides of different radicals are added to primary and secondary orthophosphates, and if mixed mixtures of different acid sulphates react with tricalcium phosphate.

At present mixed KP and NP fertilizers are made by mixing superphosphate with potassium sulphate or ammonium sulphate. It is suggested that the KP, NP and KNP fertilizers can be obtained by directly treating rock phosphate with $KHSO_4$ or NH_4HSO_4 or their mixtures in water. The amount of water may be so adjusted that the resultant product is a dry powder in a form suitable for direct transportation to the agriculturists.

The mixed phosphate mixture, containing both water-soluble alkali phosphate and citrate-soluble dicalcium phosphate will be more efficient than ordinary available fertilizers in the markets containing only water-soluble phosphates, and there is some saving of sulphuric acid in making the fertilizer.

Further work is in progress.

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